

Resistance in Chengte 232 to the two isolates tested is conditioned by a single gene that is allelic or closely linked to a gene in its progenitor, Toride 1. We conclude, therefore, that Chengte 232 inherited the gene from Toride 1.

Because Toride 1 carries *Pi-z'*, it is likely that *Pi-z'* controls the resistance in Chengte 232. The resistance genes of Tetep, however, were not transferred into Chengte 232. ■

Pest resistance—insects

Screening of rice hybrids for resistance to whitebacked planthopper, *Sogatella furcifera* (Horvath)

J. Singh, K. K. Shukla, G. S. Sidhu, S. S. Malhi, and M. R. Gagneja, Punjab Agricultural University (PAU), Ludhiana 141004, India

Twenty-four rice experimental hybrids were screened for whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) resistance at the adult plant stage under natural conditions at Bhupindra Rice Research Substation, Rauni (a hot spot of the insect at seedling stage), and under artificial conditions in a glasshouse at PAU. The field experiments were replicated three times using a

randomized complete block design. The glasshouse experiment was replicated twice using a completely randomized design.

Number of insects/10 hills in the field was counted by tapping plants. Damage was scored in the glasshouse experiment using the 0-9 scale of the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (see table).

PERH188, PERH207, PERH210, and PERH225 were found to be moderately resistant under both conditions and PERH239, PERH288, and PERH690 were considered to be susceptible.

Similar results were recorded for nearly half of the entries under both conditions. Differences, however, were noted in PERH125, PERH229,

Screening of rice hybrids under natural conditions at a hot spot in Rauni and under artificial infestation conditions, 1993 kharif.

Hybrid	Parentage	Insects/10 hills at Rauni (no.)	Damage score (0-9 scale)
PERH1	Pb.CMS 8 A/PAU1106-6-2	66	6.9
PERH2	Pb.CMS 8 A/IR31432-6-2-1R	55	7.2
PERH3	Pb.CMS 10 A/PAU1106-6-2	60	5.2
PERH7	Pb.CMS 1 A/PAU1106-6-2	44	6.6
PERH9	Pb.CMS 1 A/PAU1126-15-3-1	61	6.8
PERH38	Pb.CMS 2 A/PR106	25	5.7
PERH46	Pb.CMS 4 A/IR31432-6-2-1R	61	6.3
PERH125	Pb.CMS 8 A/IR13292-5-3	39	7.9
PERH134	Pb.CMS 8 A/PAU1126-1-1	145	5.8
PERH135	Pb.CMS 8 A/PAU1126-15-3-1	77	6.9
PERH188	Pb.CMS 10 A/PAU1106-5-4	39	4.5
PERH207	Pb.CMS 10 A/PR106	53	4.6
PERH210	Pb.CMS 1 A/IR32841-46-1-1	34	3.2
PERH225	Pb.CMS 2 A/IR32841-46-1-1	35	5.0
PERH229	Pb.CMS 2 A/PAU1106-21-4	191	4.1
PERH239	Pb.CMS 3 A/IR31432-6-2-1R	138	7.5
PERH244	Pb.CMS 3 A/PAU1106-21-4	165	3.6
PERH257	Pb.CMS 3 A/PR103	101	5.8
PERH288	Pb.CMS 8 A/PAU1126-29-1	193	8.1
PERH353	Pb.CMS 1 A/IR13292-5-3	34	6.7
PERH389	Pb.CMS 3 A/PAU1126-15-3-1	79	6.5
PERH588	Pb.CMS 1 A/IR31802-56-4	27	6.3
PERH577 A	Pb.CMS 2 A/IR31802-56-4	22	6.6
PERH690	Pb.CMS 58025 A/PAU1106-6-2	165	6.8
PR103 (check)	IR8/IR127-2-2	76	6.3
PR106 (check)	IR8//Peta*5/Belle Patna	83	8.4
PR108 (check)	Vijay/Ptb21	29	7.2
PR110 (check)	TN1/Patong 32//PR106	72	6.3

IRRN REMINDER

Reprint service. All items included in the *Rice literature update* are available at the IRRI Library and Documentation Service. Photocopies of original documents (not to exceed 40 pages) are supplied free to rice scientists of developing countries. Rice scientists elsewhere are charged US\$0.20 for each page or part of a page copied, plus postage. Payment should be in check or money order, payable to Library and Documentation Service, IRRI.

Address requests to Library and Documentation Service, IRRI, P.O. Box 933, Manila 1099, Philippines. Fax: (63-2) 817-2087, electronic mail: IN% "C.AUSTRIA@IRRI.CGNET.COM"

PERH244, PERH353, PERH588, and PERH577 A. The differential behavior of the test entries suggests that rice germplasm should be screened for reaction to WBPH under both natural and artificial conditions. ■

Screening rice accessions for resistance to thrips

M. P. Parthiban and R. Veeravel, Entomology Department, Annamalai University, Annamalaiagar 608002, Tamil Nadu, India

Thrips, *Stenchaetothrips biformis* (Bagnall), is a serious pest in rice nurseries in the tropical plains of Tamil Nadu. Both nymphs and adults can cause extensive damage to seedlings by feeding on the leaves, resulting in inward curling along the margins that can lead to scorching, wilting, and death.

In the first phase, we screened 122 accessions for reaction to thrips in the field during August 1992 and September 1993 at the Annamalai University Experimental Farm, Annamalaiagar. Each test entry was planted in moist soil in 0.7-m long rows, at a row space of 20 cm. Each entry was replicated three times, with one row per replication. Ptb33, the resistant check, and TN1, the